

nursery were planted at 3 seedlings/ hill, spaced 15 × 10 cm and 15 × 20 cm. Plot size was 6 × 3 m, with 30 cm space between plots. A 3 × 2 factorial, randomized complete block design with three replications was used.

Fertilizer and agrochemicals were applied as recommended by the Department of Agriculture. Plots were harvested after removing 2 rows around each plot, and yield estimated at 14% moisture.

Soil samples were randomly collected weekly for measuring soil pH and soil conductivity from planting to grain filling.

Highest conductivity was 6.65 dS/m when the crop was at tiller initiation.

Bw 272-8 and Pokkali had some scorching of leaf blade tips. Bw 297-2 had leaf rolling.

Heavy rains 3 to 5 wk after transplanting reduced soil conductivity, which gradually increased to 4 dS/m at flowering stage. No growth retardation or panicle sterility was observed.

Pokkali lodged (40-55%) at flowering, especially in 15- × 10-cm plots. Bw 297-2 lodged slightly in the closer spacing.

Bw 272-8 yielded significantly more than Bw 297-2, and both varieties bested Pokkali (see table). For all varieties, reducing spacing from 15 × 20 cm to 15 × 10 cm significantly increased yield.

Interaction between variety and spacing was not statistically significant.

Effect of spacing on yield of 3 transplanted varieties in saline fields. Bombuwela, Sri Lanka.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)		Variety mean
	15 × 10 cm	15 × 20 cm	
Bw 272-8	3.4	2.7	3.1
Bw 297-2	2.8	2.0	2.4
Pokkali	1.3	0.8	1.1
Spacing mean	2.5	1.9	–

LSD for variety
(0.01) – 0.7 t/ha
(0.05) – 0.5 t/ha

LSD for spacing
(0.01) – 0.6 t/ha

Results show that using resistant varieties at reduced spacing could increase yields in saline tracts. □

Integrated germplasm improvement

Nepal releases nine rice varieties

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Most Nepal ricefields (88%) lie in the tropical to subtropical climatic region that includes the Tarai region (southern plain area), 9.5% are in the midhill region up to 1,372 m, and 2.5% are in cold high hills between 1,372 and

2,316 m. Rice is cultivated up to elevations of 3,048 m.

Nepal's target rice production is 5.1 million t, averaging 3.5 t/ha, by year 2000. Improved varieties are needed to help reach this goal.

In Aug 1987, Nepal released nine varieties for different ecological regions and conditions (see table). Palung 2 is

New rice varieties recommended for ecological regions of Nepal, 1987.

Ecological region and conditions for cultivation	Recommended variety name	Original designation	Parents	Country of origin	When introduced in Nepal	Growth duration (d)	Yield (t/ha)	Grain type
<i>Temperate region</i>								
For high hills (1524-1981 m) (cold temperate region) Irrigated condition	Palung 2	NR10073-167-3-1-3	BG94-2/Pokhareli Masino		Nepal bred	158-186	4.9 - 7.2	Coarse
For midhills (914-1524 m)	Khumal 2	NR10068-60-3-2	Jarneli/KN-LB-36t BLK-2-8	Nepal	Nepal bred	130-153	3.5 - 7.7	Coarse
Warm temperate region	Khumal 4	NR10078-76-14	IR28/Pokhareli Masino	Nepal	Nepal bred	139-148	4.2 - 8.4	Coarse
<i>Tropical to subtropical region</i>								
1) Irrigated condition (610-1524 m) Early season (Feb-Jun) cultivation (Chaite Dhan Kheti)	Chaite 2	IR7151-260-3-3	BG34-8/IR2061-522-6-9 (IRRI)		1979	120-125	3.6 - 6.4	Medium
	Chaite 4	IR9729-67-3	BG34-8/IR28//IR2095-625-1-252 (IRRI)		1980	120-125	3.4 - 6.6	Medium
Normal season (Jun-Oct) cultivation (Barkhe Dhan Kheti)	Barkhe 2 Khajura 2	B4416-126-3-21 PAU41-262	C4-63 GB/B 531b-TK-39 RP72/Mutant 65	Indonesia India	1977 1979	130-140 135-145	3.5 - 5.3 3.3 - 4.7	Fine Medium
2) Rainfed lowland condition For normal season cultivation	Makwanpur 1	BG400-1	Ob 78/IR20/H4	Sri Lanka	1980	140-150	3.5 - 6.3	Coarse
3) Rainfed upland condition For normal season cultivation	Ghaiya 2	MW10	MTU/W. Kakaiku	India	1980	110-115	2.1 - 4.7	Medium

recommended for cold temperate region. Khumal 2 and Khumal 4 were selected for warm temperate regions under irrigation. Chaite 2 and Chaite 4 are

recommended for early season (Feb to Jun) and Barkhe 2 and Khajura 2 for normal season (Jun to Oct) cultivation under irrigation in tropical or

subtropical regions. Makwanpur 1 is released for rainfed lowland and Ghaiya 2 for rainfed lowland for the hot region. □

Evaluation of African Upland Rice Advanced Trial (AURAT) at Ibadan, Nigeria

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Nurseries of 17 entries in 1985 and 15 each in 1986 and 1987 were laid out during the wet season at Ibadan in a

randomized complete block design with 4 replications. Plot size was 12 m². Four to six dry seeds were dibbled at 25 × 25-cm spacing.

Eleven entries were tested over 3 yr. In 1985, moisture stress reduced plant height and grain yield. IRAT104, which possessed clean grains, significantly outyielded the check FARO 11. Yields in 1986 were variable but not significantly different. In 1987, plant

height, tillering, and grain yields generally increased because of steady rainfall throughout the growing season. ITA305, ITA3 15, IRAT170, and UPLRi-5 yielded significantly higher than FARO 11.

Four entries—ITA305, IRAT161, IRAT 104, and ITA3 15—that outyielded FARO 11 by 25% were selected for national multilocation trials. □

Data management and computer modeling

Models for panicle growth simulation

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Panicle growth simulation helps determine rate and duration of grain

filling. Using data from 1987 wet season experiments at IRRRI, we tested six growth models to find the best one for simulating panicle growth.

Richard's function performed best, with the largest regression coefficient between simulated and actual growth. Logistic function ranked second,

followed by cubic polynomial, quadratic polynomial, negative exponential, and Gompertz function. Results indicate Gompertz function is not suitable for panicle growth simulation. □

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CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Soils and soil characterization

Effect of soil type on draft force needed to plow soils of South Sulawesi, Indonesia

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We measured the draft required to pull special-purpose plows on different soils in South Sulawesi. Draft was measured with a drawbar dynamometer, three times for each soil. Carabao, cow, or human power was used, depending on site condition. Cuts were 15 cm wide

Draft of soil types in South Sulawesi, Indonesia.

Soil	Soil draft (kN)			
	Wetland		Dryland	
	Grassy	Nongrassy	Grassy	Nongrassy
Grey alluvial	0.53	0.45	0.58	0.50
Old grey alluvial	0.66	0.51	0.63	0.57
Grey brownish alluvial	0.54	0.47	0.60	0.49
Yellowish grey alluvial	0.43	0.39	0.49	0.42
Hydromorphic alluvial	0.65	0.93	0.63	0.64
Brownish grey alluvial	0.54	0.46	0.65	0.59
Brownish alluvial	0.60	0.46	0.63	0.54
Complex brown Regosol, Mediterranean, and Latosol	0.44	0.40	0.48	0.37
Latosol	0.47	0.44	0.60	0.47
Reddish brown Mediterranean	0.52	0.47	0.57	0.51
Complex reddish brown Mediterranean and Latosol	0.56	0.50	0.57	0.51

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